

D3.2 – REPORT ON THE BENDING-FORCE RELATION IN NANOPILLARS

StretchBio – Pillar Bending at the Nanoscale

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Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to demonstrate the bending of silicon nanopillars when subjected to applied forces, simulating those exerted by biological tissues. The experimental design targets a force range of 10-100 nN and a deflection range of up to 10 nm, ensuring compatibility with photonics measurements. One major challenge is the reduced size of the nanopillars, which renders conventional optical microscopy ineffective for detailed observation. To circumvent this limitation, alternative methods like Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and indirect measurements have been considered. Various methods of applying force, including centrifugal forces, direct contact, mechanical excitation, and electrostatic actuation, have been explored. However, most of these methods are either unsuitable for SEM observation or do not achieve the desired force magnitudes.

Unexpectedly, sporadic bending of nanopillars has been observed under SEM, which is attributed to electrostatic forces from the electron beam. Although this method does not fulfil all experimental requirements, it allows for direct visualization of the bending process. A redesigned pillar layout is proposed to further investigate this phenomenon. Despite the challenges, bending has successfully been achieved using the electrostatic technique within SEM, although the exact underlying mechanism remains to be elucidated.

Additionally, Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) force spectroscopy has been employed to measure mechanical deflection. While it delivers promising results, the challenges in precise modelling and prediction render the technique less suitable for our specific objectives. Nevertheless, this method holds potential for measuring tissue stiffness, which could serve as a valuable control and correlational experiment later in the project.

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1 Purpose of this document

In this report, we outline our efforts to validate the bending simulations conducted earlier in the project, as outlined in deliverable D2.1.

The primary objective of this project is to develop and test a nanosensor designed to measure the mechanical properties of tissues, particularly in tissue biopsies. The sensor operates based on the principle that changes in the mechanical properties of silicon nanopillars, which form part of a photonic crystal (PhC), will affect their optical properties. This change occurs when a tissue is placed atop the nanopillars, altering their mechanical behaviour and consequently, the optical characteristics of the PhC. The dimensions of these pillars—diameter ranging from 50-200 nm, pitch (sidewall to sidewall) from 50-200 nm, and height between 1 to 3 μm —are critical for optimizing both optical and mechanical properties and are tailored to suit specific requirements as depicted in Figure 1.

Currently, we are investigating two specific alterations in the mechanical properties of the pillars:

1. The deflection of the pillar tip occurs as the tissue interacts with it. From report D2.1, we understand that the expected tip deflection, caused by forces ranging from 10 nN to 100 nN, is on the order of tens of nanometres. This deflection is highly dependent on both the pillar's height and diameter.
2. The stiffness of the tissue may change without causing visible deformation to the pillar. In this scenario, our approach involves measuring the mechanical vibrational modes of the pillar induced by thermal excitation, with expected vibrational amplitudes of less than 1 nm.

The analysis of the pillar-tissue interaction will be fully extended in the frame of WP6 activity.

Figure 1 – Generic sketch of a silicon pillar array illustrating the dimensions relevant to the nanopillar arrays used in the project

In this deliverable, our goal is to demonstrate that silicon nanopillars within the specified dimensions will bend when subjected to a force similar to that exerted by tissues. Specifically, we aim to design an experiment in which a known force (ranging from 10 to 100 nN) is applied to the tip of a silicon nanopillar and measure the resulting deflection (approximately 10 nm). Ideally, this experiment should also allow for compatibility with optical measurements later in the project. Furthermore, it would be beneficial if the experiment could selectively bend only specific pillars within the array. Although this concept may seem straightforward, designing an experiment that meets these requirements has proven challenging, primarily due to the small size of the nanopillars required for this project.

The small dimensions of the pillars, coupled with the subtle nature of the deflections, render conventional optical microscopy ineffective for observing these changes. Instead, electron microscopy, such as Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), can be employed to visualize the deflection. However, there are significant limitations on how the pillars can be manipulated within the SEM. Alternatively, indirect methods of measuring deflection, such as dielectric measurements or laser reflection, could be employed, but these techniques require precise calibration to accurately measure the deflections.

Several methods have been considered for applying forces to the pillars, including:

- Centrifugal forces (i.e., spinning the pillars) to induce bending.
- Direct contact force, (e.g., using the tip of an Atomic Force Microscope (AFM), to push the pillars.
- Characterization via mechanical excitation (e.g., using a piezo element).
- Application of magnetic or electrostatic actuation (e.g., via integrated electrodes).

However, most of these methods are incompatible with SEM observations (such as centrifugal forces, direct contact forces, and mechanical excitation) or produce forces that are significantly lower than required (such as magnetic and centrifugal forces). Even systems with integrated electrodes would need several hundred volts to generate the necessary force magnitudes to bend the pillars, which is incompatible with SEM observation.

Figure 2 – Silicon nanopillar array with bending nanopillars observed in a SEM

During our investigations into nanostructures, we observed that nanopillars would sporadically bend when examined under a scanning electron microscope, as documented in Figure 2. We attribute this bending to electrostatic forces generated by the interaction between the nanopillars and the electron beam in the SEM (trapped electrostatic charge). Although the

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precise mechanism of this bending is extremely difficult to model, this phenomenon has provided a direct method for visualizing the bending of the pillars.

To further explore the effects of electrostatic forces on the pillars, we designed a new layout with pillars of various diameters, wall-to-wall pitches, and fabricated at two different heights. Despite not meeting all our initial requirements, this method shows promise for further development and potential future utility, as discussed in Section 2 of this report.

Additionally, we employed Atomic Force Microscopy to perform force spectroscopy on the surfaces of nanopillars. While force spectroscopy is a well-established technique in AFM, its application in measuring mechanical deflection of nanopillars is relatively novel. The challenges we faced include accurately modelling the mechanical system of the cantilever and the pillar and precisely predicting the contact point between them. Our findings and efforts with this technique are detailed in section 3.

2 Electrostatic bending in SEM

2.1 Experimental method

2.1.1 Chip design and fabrication

The fabrication process for the nanopillars used in the electrostatic bending experiments is consistent with the methods outlined in deliverable D3.1 (section 2.5). The process includes the following steps:

1. Spin coating a 4-inch silicon wafer with e-beam resist (CSAR AR-P 6200).
2. Using a Jeol JBX-9500-FS electron beam writer to expose the desired pattern.
3. Developing the resist, followed by depositing a 20 nm layer of Aluminum and performing a lift-off to create an etch mask.
4. Performing reactive ion etching with a mixture of C₄F₈ and SF₆ gases to etch the structures.

This fabrication technique is highly adaptable, allowing for the creation of nanopillars of various heights.

The resulting samples consist of square arrays of nanopillars with diameters ranging from 50 nm to 200 nm, increasing in steps of 25 nm, and wall-to-wall pitches from 50 nm to 200 nm, as illustrated in Figure 3. Each array spans an area of approximately 10 μm x 10 μm . The designs include labels for easy identification of each array's pitch (p) and diameter (d), for example, "d200 p200" denotes pillars with a diameter of 200 nm and a pitch of 200 nm.

To produce samples with two distinct pillar heights, the duration of the reactive ion etching step was varied, resulting in pillar heights of 1.1 μm and 2.0 μm , respectively.

Figure 3 – Sketch of the applied E-beam lithography mask. A 7x7 grid of pillars arrays with diameter ranging from 50 nm to 200 nm, and wall-to-wall pitch ranging from 50 nm to 200 nm

2.1.2 Measurements in the SEM

The SEM employed to inspect the sample is a Zeiss Supra 40VP, operated using SmartSEM software version 6.0 (Figure 4a). The silicon pillar sample is secured to the SEM holder using small metal clips (Figure 4b) and placed inside the SEM chamber. The SEM is operated in High Vacuum mode, achieving pressures lower than $2e-4$ mbar, typically reaching down to $1e-6$ mbar. The acceleration voltage applied during the examination was 15 kV.

Figure 4 – a) Overview of the Supra 40VP SEM from Zeiss. b) Image of the sample holder used to fixate the sample before placing them in the SEM chamber. Both images are courtesy of DTU Nanolab.

Several identical copies of the pillar arrays were fabricated on each sample. Initially, one copy was utilized to adjust the SEM's focus, after which the stage was moved to another copy for examination. Typically, the nanopillars begin to bend towards each other soon after exposure to the electron beam, occurring as individual events rather than simultaneously. We have captured several videos of this phenomenon to illustrate these events, which will be available on Zenodo¹.

To ensure comprehensive exposure of the nanopillar array, one or more arrays—with specific diameters and pitches—were continuously exposed to the electron beam in a top-down view. The stage of the SEM was held stationary until no further bending events were observed, after which an image of the array was acquired.

2.2 Results

2.2.1 Bending predictions from deliverable D2.1

In Figure 5, two plots from a previous deliverable (D2.1) are presented. Figure 5a displays results from a COMSOL simulation that predicts the expected tip deflection of a nanopillar with various heights and radii when a force of 15 nN is applied. The simulation indicates that the expected

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/stretchbio/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

tip deflection ranges from 1 to 100 nm, with the deflection significantly influenced by both the height and radius of the pillar. Figure 5b illustrates a similar plot, showing deflection as a function of force for a nanopillar with a fixed radius. Overall, it is expected that a pillar with a diameter of 90 nm will bend between 10 to 100 nm when a force ranging from 10 to 20 nN is applied. For a detailed description of the simulation setup, refer to deliverable D2.1.

Figure 5 – Figure 3 (a) and Figure 6 (b) from D2.1. a) COMSOL simulation of the displacement vs pillar radius for an applied force of 15 nN. b) COMSOL simulation of the maximum tip displacement as a function of applied force for a silicon pillar of 45 nm radius at four pillar heights

2.2.2 Results of bending in the SEM

Figure 6 provides an overview of the 7x7 grid of nanopillar arrays, each 2.0 μm in height. In this sample, the pillars with smaller diameters (d50 and d75) collapsed during the etching process. The "interference pattern" observed in several of the pillar arrays is an artifact of image compression and does not accurately represent the appearance of the pillars, as can be confirmed by increasing the magnification in the SEM images.

Figure 6 – Top down overview of the fabricated 7x7 grid of nanopillar arrays. The nanopillars in the image have a height of 2.0 μm

Figure 7a shows a tilted view of a single nanopillar array (d50, p100) where bending of the nanopillars is clearly seen. A close-up of the same structure is seen in Figure 7b.

Figure 7 – a) Tilted view (35°) of a single nanopillar array with a wall-to-wall pitch of 100 nm and a nanopillar diameter of 50 nm. b) magnified view of the same structure where the bent nanopillars are clearly seen.

Figure 8 show a side-by-side view of two nanopillar arrays (height 2.0 μm) with equal wall-to-wall pitch but different diameters (100 nm and 125 nm). It is seen that while the majority of the pillars with a diameter of 100 nm bend towards each other, this is not the case for pillars with a diameter of 125 nm. As expected, the pillars with the larger diameter are harder to bend compared to the narrower pillars.

Figure 8 – a) Top view of nanopillar arrays with height 2.0 μm , wall-to wall pitch of 50 nm, and nanopillar diameter of a) 125 nm and b) 100 nm.

Figure 9 shows the top-down view of pillar array from both the 1.1 μm sample and the 2.0 μm sample. It is seen that 1.1 μm pillars bend in the SEM when they have a diameter of 50 nm but not at a diameter of 75 nm. As the wall-to-wall pitch is increased, fewer bending events are seen. Similarly, for the 2.0 μm tall pillars, bending is seen for diameters of 100nm, but not for 125 nm.

Figure 9 – Top view of pillar arrays exposed to electron beam untill no further bending events could be seen. Left column for pillars of 2.0 μm height, right for pillars of 1.11 μm height.

Figure 8 demonstrates that the bending behaviour of the nanopillars aligns with expected trends, where taller and narrower pillars are more prone to bend. Additionally, as anticipated, taller pillars exhibit bending at larger diameters. A significant observation is the influence of the wall-to-wall pitch on the bending behaviour of the pillars. Increasing the pitch decreases the number of bending pillars, suggesting that the forces causing bending are applied at the surface of the pillars. In this experiment, they are electrostatic forces, due to excess surface charge.

Another interesting observation is that as the distance between the pillars increases, the bending events tend to be more concentrated in the centre of the pillar array. This could be attributed to several factors, including non-uniform etching depth across the array, which may result in slightly taller pillars in the middle, variations in the cross-section of the pillars affecting their bending behaviour, or a charging effect that impacts the entire array rather than individual pillars. Further investigations are necessary to pinpoint the precise cause of this behaviour.

The findings from Figure 8 provide valuable insights into the bending dynamics of the pillars and underscore the importance of continued research to fully understand the mechanisms behind this behaviour. Although there are unknown factors, the observed bending behaviour adheres to the expected trends and supports the hypothesis that surface effects, in our set-up electrostatic forces, play a crucial role in the bending of these pillars.

2.2.3 Comparison to predictions

To estimate the bending force required to displace the nanopillars halfway towards their nearest neighbour (half the wall-to-wall pitch), we employ the beam bending equation, as previously discussed in deliverable D2.1:

$$F = \frac{3EI}{L^3} \Delta x, \quad I = \frac{\pi}{4} \left(\frac{D}{2}\right)^4 \quad (1)$$

where E is Young's modulus, I is the second moment of inertia, L is the length (i.e. height) of the pillar, D is the pillar diameter, and Δx is the displacement of the tip of the pillar.

This is obviously a rough estimate of the force since it is clear from the SEM images (e.g., in Figure 9) that the pillars do not always bend only to one neighbour and not always equally half the distance. However, this approach should work to give us a rough idea of the magnitude of the forces applied. The calculated forces can be found in Figure 10.

		Height = 2030						
		Diameter						
		200	175	150	125	100	75	50
Pitch	50	92	54	29	14	6	2	0
	75	137	80	43	21	9	3	1
	100	183	107	58	28	11	4	1
	125	229	134	72	35	14	5	1
	150	275	161	87	42	17	5	1
	175	320	188	101	49	20	6	1
	200	366	215	116	56	23	7	1

		Height = 1114						
		Diameter						
		200	175	150	125	100	75	50
Pitch	50	554	325	175	85	35	11	2
	75	831	487	263	127	52	16	3
	100	1108	649	351	169	69	22	4
	125	1385	812	438	211	87	27	5
	150	1662	974	526	254	104	33	6
	175	1939	1136	613	296	121	38	8
	200	2216	1299	701	338	138	44	9

Figure 10 – Bending matrix showing the calculated force necessary to displace the tip of a nanopillar half the wall-to-wall distance for pitches and diameters corresponding to the 7x7 grid in the fabricated samples. The number in each grid point corresponds to the required force in nN. a) for pillars with a height of 2.0 μm , b) for pillars with a height of 1.1 μm . The color indicates whether the pillars in the fabricated sample were observed to bend (**green**) or not bend (**red**). White squares mean that the result is unclear and grey squares that the pillars were damaged in the fabrication.

We see that the pillars where we observe bending events would require a force in the range of 2-17 nN.

3 Bending using AFM

Bending of pillars in AFM is measured using a force spectroscopy technique. During the measurement, the AFM tip approaches the substrate, pushes the sample and then retracts, as shown in Figure 11. The signal obtained from the photodiode (in mV) is then converted into a cantilever deflection by multiplying the cantilever's deflection sensitivity (in nm/V) with the photodiode signal. The pillar deflection (bending) is calculated using equations given below (originally from [2]).

Figure 11 Force-distance approach (blue) and retract (red) curves for an AFM tip in contact with a) the substrate and b) the pillar. (Figure adapted from [2])

Lateral force ($F_{N,xy}^*$) applied on the pillar,

$$F_{N,xy}^* = F_N^* \cos \gamma^* \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

$$F_N^* = \frac{k^* d_{c,z}}{\sin \gamma^* - \frac{3}{2} \frac{(h_{tip} + \frac{1}{2} h_{pillar})}{L} \sin \beta^* \cos \gamma^*} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

$$\frac{1}{k^*} = \frac{1}{k_{c,z}} + \frac{1}{k_{pillar}} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

k^* is the combined spring constant of the cantilever and the nanopillar (slope of approach curve), $k_{c,z}$ is the spring constant of the cantilever (obtained using the thermal tune method), k_{pillar} is the spring constant of the nanopillar, $d_{c,z}$ is cantilever deflection which is product of deflection sensitivity and photodiode signal, β^* is the half front angle of the base of the pyramidal AFM tip, γ^* is the angle of the inclination of the wall of the tip relative to its vertical axis, h_{tip} is the height

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of the pyramidal tip, h_{pillar} is the height of the pillar, t is the thickness of the cantilever, L is the length of the cantilever.

After obtaining the lateral force ($F_{N,xy}^*$) and the spring constant of the nanopillar (k_{pillar}) from AFM force spectroscopy measurement, the pillar deflections (d_{pillar}) can be calculated using equation below,

$$d_{pillar} = F_{N,xy}^*/k_{pillar} \quad (Eq. 5)$$

The AFM measurements are performed using a Nanosurf Drive AFM. A PPP-NCLR probe (Nanosensors) is used (shown in Figure 12) with a cantilever length of 230 μm , a width of 34 μm and a thickness of 7 μm . The tip of the probe is made of highly doped silicon with a height (h_{tip}) of 12 μm and a length of 5 μm . The deflection sensitivity and the spring constant of the cantilever ($k_{c,z}$) are determined prior to the measurement. The deflection sensitivity of the cantilever is 320.5 nm/V and the spring constant of the cantilever ($k_{c,z}$) is 19.9 N/m.

Figure 12 – SEM image of the cantilever used for the force spectroscopy measurements.

Figure 13 – Microscope image of the sample and the cantilever.

The sample for the measurement consists of two regions: flat silicon region and nanopillar array, as shown in Figure 13. The nanopillar’s diameter is 200 nm and the height, 1.5 μm . A scan area is defined near the flat silicon/nanopillar boundary and a force-distance curve is obtained at each point defined in the scan area.

Figure 14 – Force-distance curve when tip interacts with the silicon substrate

Figure 15 – Force-distance curve when tip interacts with the nanopillar

The force-distance curves obtained after force spectroscopy measurements are shown in Figure 14 for flat silicon substrate and in Figure 15 for the nanopillar. The raw data is given in the units of mV, which is the signal from the photodiode. For the maximum photodiode signal of 312 mV used in this measurement, maximum lateral force ($F_{N,xy}^*$) on the nanopillar is calculated to be 2.76 μN using Eq. 2 and Eq. 3. The combined spring constant (k^*) is obtained from the slope of the approach curve (black curve in Figure 15), whose value is 6.37 N/m. Later, the spring

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constant of the nanopillar (k_{pillar}) is calculated to be 9.37 N/m using Eq. 4. Finally, the deflection of the pillar for the maximum lateral force ($F_{N,xy}^*$) is found to be 294.5 nm using Eq. 5.

For the same value of lateral force (2.76 μ N) and same dimensions of the nanopillar, the deflection of the nanopillar is calculated using the theoretical beam bending formula mentioned earlier (Eq. 1). With Young's modulus of silicon expected to vary from 120 GPa to 170 GPa, the theoretically expected range of deflection of the nanopillar is from 232.5 nm to 329.5. We see that the experimentally determined deflection falls well within this range.

4 Conclusion and next steps

In conclusion, our study on bending nanopillars while simultaneously measuring force and deflection proved to be significantly more challenging than originally anticipated. The small size of the nanopillars makes direct and precise measurements of deflection (in the range of 10 nm) and force (in the range of 10 nN) very difficult. Despite these difficulties, we successfully achieved bending of the nanopillar using an electrostatic technique within an SEM, although the exact mechanism of this bending remains unclear. The real-time bending observed in the SEM suggests a build-up of charge in the silicon pillars due to exposure to the electron beam. However, the attractive nature of the force indicates that the charge distribution is not uniform.

A second force measurement approach curves performed in an AFM provided promising results, but complexities in modelling the mechanical interface with the nanopillar hindered further progress. Nonetheless, our experiments validated the correlation between predicted and observed bending forces, which is in agreement with the growing use of AFM mapping for tissue and cell stiffness mapping.

Both techniques confirm that the pillars bend within the range of forces predicted in deliverable D2.1. Importantly, neither of the explored techniques can be applied simultaneously with optical measurements of the photonic crystal properties. Such measurements must be conducted separately.

The outcome of the deliverable, despite the challenges in achieving precise measurements, is that the nanopillars fabricated as part of the StretchBio project can bend and potentially vibrate when exposed to external excitation inputs. This is a crucial finding as it avoids the use of rigid structures that might hinder the future development of the StretchBio prototype. These flexible characteristics ensure that the pillars can respond adaptively in real-world applications, aligning with the project's objectives to create a dynamic and responsive device.

5 References

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6 Glossary

Abbreviation	Explanation
DX.Y	Deliverable X.Y
PhC	Photonic Crystal
AFM	Atomic Force Microscopy
nV	Nano Volt
μ V	Micro Volt
mV	Milli Volt
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
nm	Nanometre
μ m	Micrometre
kV	Kilo Volt
GPa	Giga Pascal

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